

Finding Parse Errors in the Midst of Parse Errors

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Abstract

We consider a simple method for dependency parse error detection and develop representations which account for parse errors occurring in the context of other parse errors. The core insight is to combine both very detailed representations with more relaxed representations, i.e., ones which allow for errors. We show that for situations with little annotated data to begin with, error detection precision can be greatly increased.

1 Introduction

Parse error detection is useful for improving the quality of large corpora via a semi-automatic correction process [2, 8], for assisting in automatic parse revision [11], and for selecting sentences for active learning [14]. Yet there are few methods for automatic parse error detection, and some are tailored to particular annotation schemes or parsers [e.g., 1, 2]. We consider a simple method for dependency parse error detection and develop representations which account for parse errors occurring in the context of other parse errors [9, 10]. Although our work focuses on one particular method [8], the method is general-purpose and language and parser-independent, and the insights should be applicable to general parse improvement.

Our contributions start with identifying the core reasons for how anomalies are identified in an error detection method [8], in section 2. This analysis highlights how new insights can be integrated and shows why the method is well-suited for situations with little annotated data to learn from. We then outline in general terms how surrounding errors occur in parses, in the beginning of section 3. Such surrounding errors are problematic because methods use full parse information to detect anomalies, and an error in one part affects finding an error in another part. While a human annotator may focus on a sentence-by-sentence correction and thus identify surrounding errors on the basis of one identified error, surrounding errors nonetheless can lead to a decrease in error detection precision and/or a misjudgment in how severe an error is. Furthermore, for tasks such as parse correction, there may be no human involved in the correction process.

Building on the types of surrounding errors, we propose in the rest of section 3 new information to include in the model, which increases the precision of the method for a workable portion of the corpus, as shown in the evaluation in section 4. The core insight is to combine both very detailed representations with more relaxed representations, i.e., ones which allow for errors.

2 Parse error detection

2.1 The DAPS method

The method in [8] detects anomalous parse structures (DAPS), using n -gram sequences of dependency structures. The training corpus is reduced to a set of rules that consist of a head and its dependents, and then the rules from the parsed testing corpus are scored based on their similarity to rules from training, for heads of the same category. This is a rather simple method (discussed below), but it serves the linguistic function of identifying anomalies in word valency [17].

For example, consider the partial tree in figure 1 from the Wall Street Journal (WSJ) portion of the Penn Treebank [12], converted to dependencies with the Stanford CoreNLP tool [4]. From this tree, rules are extracted as in (1), where all dependents of the NNS head (-H) are realized.

Figure 1: A sketch of a basic dependency tree

$$(1) \text{ pobj} \rightarrow \text{num:CD NNS-H prep:IN}$$

Such a parsed rule is then broken down into its component n -grams and compared to rules from training, using the formula for scoring an item (e_i) in (2). N -gram counts ($C(ngrm)$) come from the same corpus used to train the parser. An instantiation for this rule is in (3), where we obtain a score for the `prep:IN` in (1). Tokens are ranked by score, with lower scores more likely to be errors.

$$(2) \quad s_{base}(e_i) = \sum_{ngrm:e_i \in ngrm \wedge n \geq 2} C(ngrm)$$

$$(3) \quad s_{base}(\text{prep:IN}) = C(\text{NNS prep:IN}) + C(\text{prep:IN END}) \\ + C(\text{num:CD NNS prep:IN}) + C(\text{NNS prep:IN END}) \\ + C(\text{START num:CD NNS prep:IN}) \\ + C(\text{num:CD NNS prep:IN END}) \\ + C(\text{START num:CD NNS prep:IN END})$$

We use two scoring variants: 1) the high-gram method (*high*) uses all n -grams of length 3 or greater ($n \geq 3$), as bigrams do not encode much context [8]; and 2) a weighted version of an all-gram method (*wall*), which multiplies bigram counts by a dampening weight of 0.01: thus, if a rule lacks a bigram, it is more likely that the rule is of poor quality than if it simply lacked a trigram [see also 11].¹

2.2 Analysis of the method

The method is simple: count up n -grams of varying lengths. While there are reasons to consider using more sophisticated methods in the future (e.g., tree kernels [15]), this framework has its advantages. First, it is relatively quick to run; it is easy to replicate; and the output is interpretable. Furthermore, it seems to be effective across a variety of conditions, including for manual annotation. This fits with the general notion that effective error detection methods, acting as sanity checks on complicated processes, are often relatively simple [6]. Secondly, it allows for arbitrarily long and complex pieces of information. Thirdly, it handles small amounts of data well, even with large numbers of unique n -grams.

The method counts up features (n -grams) during training and then points out in the parse those positions whose features have very low counts, often zero. In other words, the positions identified are those whose features are sparse. If more features are added, the chance of accidentally obtaining a low score is decreased, potentially increasing precision—assuming that the features are truly informative. The benefit for scenarios with small amounts of annotated data is that, while there may be few ways to gather new data, there are new ways to splice up the data one already has. We investigate some of these new ways in this paper.

3 Accounting for contextual errors

One problem with the method as it stands stems from errors occurring together in the same rule: an item’s (in)validity may be clouded by an erroneous sister. In the constructed (4), for instance, the validity of DT:Det attaching to the Noun head is occluded by the presence of the erroneous MOD:Adv. Instead of DT:Det MOD:Adj Noun-H, we get DT:Det MOD:Adv MOD:Adj, a trigram absent from training. In this particular case, then, we may unfairly flag DT:Det as an error.

(4) **DT:Det MOD:Adv MOD:Adj Noun-H**

Our goal is to account for erroneous contextual items (i.e., sister dependents) in scoring a rule. Types of contextual errors include:

1. (a) **Mislabeling:** A dependency has the wrong dependency label (A Y:X C should be A Z:X C).

¹The code here implements *high* by default and requires only minor modification for *wall*: <http://cl.indiana.edu/~md7/papers/dickinson-smith11.html>

- (b) **Mistagging:** A dependency has the wrong POS label (A Y:X C should be A Y:W C).
2. **Substitution:** A dependency has the wrong attachment, but something else could go in this position with this head (A B C should be A D C).
 3. **Comission:** A dependency has the wrong attachment, but nothing else goes in this position with this head (A B C should be A C).
 4. **Omission:** There is a missing attachment (A C should be A B C).

We approach the errors by adding n -grams that reflect each type of change, essentially compiling out Levenshtein edits. Given the analysis of the method above, the effect of adding more n -grams should serve to increase *precision*, not recall, of errors found: since each dependency relation now has more chances to obtain a higher score, we expect fewer which are still low-scoring, but those cases should be more accurate. Note that: a) each solution is restricted to a single type of edit, some of which are partial substitutions; and b) modifications are for all n -grams, not just the rule as a whole [5]. The set-up of adding new n -grams also makes clear that the issue is fundamentally one of representation.

Focusing on representation, we hope, makes the insights applicable to other domains, in the same way that representations for corpus annotation error detection have led to, e.g., particular features for native language identification [3] and methods for uncovering annotation definitions [7]. Additionally, although we have only tried individual solutions, future work can explore combinations of solutions; initial results indicate that not all combinations are favorable.

Solution #1a: Removing a dependency label For potentially incorrect dependency labels, our solution is to include n -grams which replace a dependency:POS pair with only the POS. Recalling the base formula for calculating an anomaly score in (2) and using a set of modified n -grams N' , the formula is given in (5) and an instantiation in (6). Here, the POS CD replaces `num:CD`.

$$(5) \quad s(e_i) = s_{base} + \sum_{ngm' \in N' \wedge ngm': e_i \in ngm' \wedge n \geq 3} C(ngm')$$

$$(6) \quad \begin{aligned} s(\text{prep:IN}) &= s_{base}(\text{prep:IN}) \\ &+ C(\text{CD NNS-H prep:IN}) \\ &+ C(\text{START CD NNS-H prep:IN}) \\ &+ C(\text{CD NNS-H prep:IN END}) \\ &+ C(\text{START CD NNS-H prep:IN END}) \end{aligned}$$

The set of modifications N' is subject to constraints. First, only one item in a rule is replaced at a time. Thus, we obtain `START CD NNS-H prep:IN END` and `START num:CD NNS-H IN END`, but not `START CD NNS-H IN END`. This keeps the number of new n -grams manageable and reflects the assumption that it is less likely

for there to be multiple contextual errors. The second constraint is not to allow heads to be modified—more of an issue when using a dummy label (solution #2) or removing the item entirely (solution #3). We restrict this because the comparison of rules is based on having similar heads; e.g., only rules with NNS heads are compared to the rule in (1). The third constraint only applies when an item is removed (solution #3): items on the edge of an n -gram are not allowed to be removed. In this case, we wind up with an already-known bigram, e.g., `num:CD NNS-H prep:IN` becomes `NNS-H prep:IN`. Relatedly, for all solutions we do not modify any bigrams (e.g., `CD NNS-H`), given the questionable nature of bigrams.

Solution #1b: Removing a POS label Having a wrong POS label (A Y:X C should be A Y:W C) seems at first glance to be mainly a concern for when automatic POS tagging is employed, but, as example (4) illustrates, sometimes the root of an inconsistency can be traced to an improper POS tag (e.g., the problem for (4) is the presence of the Adv(erb) POS tag). We thus remove the POS tag and keep the dependency label (e.g., in (6) replace every `CD` with `num`).

Solution #2: Skipping items To handle an incorrectly-attached sister item when some other item could attach in this position (e.g., A M:X C should be A N:Y C), we replace items in a rule with a dummy token (`SKIP`) (e.g., `START SKIP NNS-H prep:IN`). This solution is fairly broad, as the dummy `SKIP` stands in for any substituted item (including relabelings, as in solution #1a), as well as the original item.

Solution #3: Removing items When a dependency has the wrong attachment, but nothing else goes in this position (e.g., A B C should be A C), the simple modification is to remove a potentially erroneous context item (e.g., B). However, training and testing must be handled differently, as removing an item in training would be an incorrect sequence (e.g., A C in this case). Thus, we obtain training rules in the basic way (s_{base} in (3)), and then in testing add rules which remove an item.

Solution #4: Inserting items Items which should have been attached to a head (e.g., A C should be A B C) lead to positing the insertion of an item between two other items in a rule. While we might want to posit every single intervening token, with every possible label, as the inserted item (B), this is cumbersome. For this exploration, we simply ask whether *something* could be inserted between the two items. Training consists of generating extra n -grams with dummy `SKIPS` appropriately inserted, exactly as in solution #2. For testing, we then insert `SKIP` items between items in a rule if there is an item between them in the linear string (A `SKIP` C). If neighboring items in a rule are linearly adjacent, no `SKIP` is inserted.

Context changes vs. revision checking The methods of changing items are different than the revision checking algorithm in [8], in that they account for contextual errors, whereas revision checking rescores the item in focus. To examine the

score of A in A B C, for instance, the current solutions simulate a change to B or C to see how that affects the score of A, whereas revision checking notes the effect of revising A. Context item changing is rather robust, in that it subsumes rules the system has not seen before. For example, generalizing A B C to A SKIP C covers A D C, too, which may have never been seen before. Thus, the scoring may also be of help for new rules within new kinds of data.

4 Evaluation

4.1 Experimental conditions

We use the WSJ corpus [12] for all experiments, converted to the Stanford dependencies [4], allowing us to vary the training data size and keep constant the testing data. In particular, we train both the parsers and the error detection methods on a small portion of the corpus (section 02) and a larger portion (sections 02–15), and then test on section 00. To increase the variety in parser quality, we use two parsers with differing methods, MaltParser [16] and MSTParser [13]. This set-up is in line with recommendations in [18] for selecting appropriate experimental conditions to robustly test error detection methods.

Error detection precision is given in table 1, i.e., the percentage of parser errors accurately identified for corpus positions under a threshold. Since each method identifies a differing number of positions at differing thresholds, we report precision for *segment sizes*: for the lowest-scoring 5% of tokens, for example, what is precision across the methods? Since the number of positions is fixed for a given segment, an increase in precision means there is a corresponding increase in recall for that segment [18]. We choose low segment sizes (1% and 5% of the testing corpus) because activities like manually correcting annotation for a huge amount of text rely on high precision for a relatively small percentage of the data [18].

4.2 Results

Turning to the trends in table 1, we note a number of things. 1) For small training (02), it almost always helps to have some new representation, i.e., multiple representations indeed work better for situations with little annotated data. This matches our analysis of the method (section 2.2), where multiple perspectives on the data provide more opportunities to pinpoint a spot as erroneous.

2) For large training (02-15), adding the new representations generally helps for checking a small amount of data (1% segment), but becomes less beneficial as more corpus positions are examined (5%). Indeed, precision goes *up* for the 1% segment, but significantly *down* for the 5% segment in moving from the small (02) to the large (02-15) training scenario.

In table 2, which reports the score thresholds for each condition, we can see part of the reason for the downward trends: as more information is added to the model—adding bigrams (moving from High to Wall), adding new representations

		1% seg.		Train: 02		Train: 02-15				5% seg.		Train: 02		Train: 02-15	
		Condition		Malt	MST	Malt	MST			Malt	MST	Malt	MST	Malt	MST
High	Base	77.0	73.6	86.7	78.7	Base	77.0	73.6	66.8	62.5					
	No-dep	79.4	76.5	89.8	83.4	No-dep	79.4	76.5	65.7	61.3					
	No-POS	83.5	78.4	91.8	82.8	No-POS	81.6	77.4	65.4	62.1					
	Skip	90.2	84.6	95.2	74.4	Skip	77.0	71.4	59.8	51.9					
	Remove	84.0	80.0	92.9	83.1	Remove	79.8	74.0	66.0	57.0					
	Insert	78.7	75.2	88.0	78.5	Insert	78.1	75.2	66.3	59.8					
Wall	Base	91.2	83.7	93.1	81.8	Base	80.4	76.0	66.6	60.7					
	No-dep	91.5	85.0	93.9	83.8	No-dep	80.4	77.1	65.9	60.5					
	No-POS	92.5	85.0	94.6	84.0	No-POS	81.3	77.9	65.2	61.4					
	Skip	94.1	88.5	94.3	75.5	Skip	78.4	71.3	59.8	51.6					
	Remove	91.5	88.1	94.3	81.6	Remove	81.0	75.2	65.4	56.9					
	Insert	92.5	84.4	92.8	65.7	Insert	77.3	67.2	59.8	47.8					

Table 1: Precision (%) for 1% & 5% segments (1342 & 6710 positions). Baseline LAS: Malt.02: 81.1%, Malt.02-15: 86.4%, MST.02: 80.5%, MST.02-15: 87.6%.

(comparing Base to other models), or, most crucially, adding more training data and thus more training rules (moving from 02 to 02-15)—the score threshold required to hit 1% or 5% of the data rises, in some cases dramatically. The reason for this is straightforward: by including information from a greater number of (training) rules, the chance of having a low score for a parsed rule is less likely. A score of 158.92, for the Malt.02-15.Wall.Skip case, for example, means that many of the rules flagged here as errors have a great deal of supporting evidence (roughly speaking, 158 instances from the training data support it), and so we should not be surprised that many of the cases are not errors, i.e., precision is low.

The upshot is that multiple representations work best for increasing precision when low-scoring positions account for a large percentage of the data to be corrected, and this tends to happen when: a) the amount of training data is small, and/or b) the amount of data to be corrected is a small percentage of the corpus. (For very large corpora, a small percentage of the corpus is still a large absolute number of positions.) Following the mathematical reasoning above, when more representations are added, a position is unlikely to get a low score by chance, and so low scores mean more, i.e., are more likely to truly indicate errors. The 1% segments confirm this: precision is high for every condition where the score threshold is around zero, whereas the higher thresholds for the Skip (14.11) and Insert (8.05) models lead to lower precision (74.4% and 65.7%, respectively).

Turning to the generally improved precision for the 02-15 training experiments with the 1% segments (vs. 02 training), we believe this improvement stems from the fact that the set of training rules is more accurate. The method is still examining zero-scoring rules, but, as compared to the 02 training experiments, more training data gives a better representation of what an acceptable rule is, and so the zero scores seem to be more meaningful.

1% seg.		Train: 02		Train: 02-15		5% seg.		Train: 02		Train: 02-15	
Condition		Malt	MST	Malt	MST	Condition		Malt	MST	Malt	MST
High	Base	0	0	0	0	Base	4	4	16	14	
	No-dep	0	0	0	0	No-dep	4	4	42	42	
	No-POS	0	0	0	0	No-POS	4	4	63	51	
	Skip	0	0	2	13	Skip	7	10	156	176	
	Remove	0	0	0	1	Remove	4	4	41	45	
	Insert	0	0	0	0	Insert	4	4	27	28	
Wall	Base	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.37	Base	0.19	0.45	20.81	19.97	
	No-dep	0.00	0.00	0.04	1.03	No-dep	0.52	1.15	46.32	48.35	
	No-POS	0.00	0.00	0.13	1.33	No-POS	2.01	1.83	67.20	59.42	
	Skip	0.00	0.00	3.14	14.11	Skip	7.04	11.04	158.92	182.29	
	Remove	0.00	0.00	0.20	2.31	Remove	1.29	2.13	45.23	49.51	
	Insert	0.00	0.00	1.05	8.05	Insert	3.05	6.05	80.59	95.44	

Table 2: Score thresholds for 1% & 5% segments (1342 & 6710 positions).

3) The more beneficial models seem to be the ones which maintain the attachments in a rule but make them more abstract (No-dep, No-POS, Skip), and not the models which attempt to actually modify the attachments of the rules (Remove, Insert). This is not necessarily tied in to the score thresholds, either: notice how the No-POS model performs better than the Remove model for MST.02-15.Wall with a 5% segment (table 1: 61.4% vs. 56.9%), but actually has a higher score threshold (table 2: 59.42 vs. 49.51). The difference here is in how closely tied the representation is to the data: for No-POS, there is a slight bit of abstraction for an element which is already present in the parse, whereas the Remove model completely changes the elements in the rule. The simplicity of the DAPS method likely means that it is risky to deviate too far from the original parses without utilizing further information.

4) Comparing the High and Wall methods confirms a finding in [18], namely: Wall methods tend to work better than High when less training data is involved, but then the two methods are more equivalent for greater amounts of training data. This underscores the main thrust of our analysis here: when there is less training data, it helps to provide additional representations, whether in the form of bigrams or in abstracted n -gram representations.

This comparison also raises the issue of how best to use the abstract representations: for bigrams, we used a weight of 0.01 and found good results. While precision is not better for higher thresholds, it is at least not generally worse than the High method. It seems, then, that it might be fruitful to explore weighting the abstract representation; indeed, it may help for all n -grams to explore a more proper weighting system, e.g., experimentally determining the optimal weights.

5 Conclusion

Building from the simple DAPS method for dependency parse error detection, we developed representations which account for parse errors occurring in the context of other parse errors. The core insight is to combine both very detailed representations with more relaxed representations, i.e., ones which allow for errors. We have shown that for situations with little annotated data to begin with, error detection precision can be greatly increased. How one evaluates crucially affects the conclusions to be drawn, underscoring the point in [18] that many different corpus settings need to be employed.

Within the DAPS method, there are several avenues to explore: even richer representations, e.g., incorporating lexical information, grandparent information, etc.; different methods of comparing and combining information (e.g., tree kernels); schemes for weighting information; and so forth. Additionally, by accounting for incorrect context, we hope to not only develop better error detection models, but also to get one step closer to developing a parse corrector, which will need to account for multiple, interrelated errors.

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